

EU-DREAM

Effective Uptake of Digital Services to Repower European
Consumers and Communities as Active Participants in Energy
Transition and Markets

D3.2 Data Sharing Interoperability

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ACRONYMS

ACRONYMS	
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
DDIM	Data-Driven Infrastructure Management
DL	DL
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
DRF	Django REST Framework
DT	Digital Twin
EMS	Energy Management System
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
IOT	Internet of Things
LL	Living Lab
LLM	Large Language Model
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OWL	Web Ontology Language
RT	Real Twin
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RDFS	RDF Schema
SAREF	Smart Applications REference
WP	Work Package
WT	Wind Turbine

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable outlines the architecture and implementation of the EU-DREAM **data space**, encompassing the semantic framework and linked data infrastructure necessary for the integration and **interoperability** of heterogeneous datasets.

Central to this infrastructure is the semantic broker, which acts as an intermediary layer, harmonizing and interlinking data originating from multiple upstream connectors. These connectors interface with diverse data sources involved in the collection processes, feeding into a unified data lake that supports the Digital Twin and optimization modules of the system. The NLP mediator interacts with the Data Platform to extract relevant information, enabling further integration and analysis. The infrastructure is designed to accommodate a wide variety of data formats and structures, including support for customized data integrations where necessary.

This deliverable is prepared to summarize the outcomes of Task 3.2 and contributes to the broader objective of establishing a scalable, semantically coherent, and interoperable data ecosystem within the EU-DREAM project.

The document is organized to guide the reader from foundational concepts to technical implementation. After an introductory section outlining the purpose, scope, and interdependencies with other work packages, it provides essential background on big data management, data interoperability, and challenges related to heterogeneous data sources. Key concepts from the Semantic Web and relevant query languages, such as SPARQL (for retrieving and manipulating RDF data) and Cypher (for navigating and extracting information from graph databases), are introduced to underpin the EU-DREAM project's semantic approach.

Subsequent sections detail the data sources available across the EU-DREAM pilots, with particular emphasis on the Dynamic District Management Server (DDIM) and its integration with other architectural components. A user guide is included to facilitate interaction with the system, followed by detailed chapters on the integration of data sources and ontologies. The alignment of incoming data with ontological concepts is addressed to ensure semantic consistency, and provisions for user interaction and accessibility are described.

The document concludes with a summary of the work accomplished and outlines directions for future development, with supporting references and annexes provided to ensure completeness and traceability.

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Introduction

The ongoing energy transition is transforming the way citizens, communities, and markets interact. Rising decentralization, digitalization, and the integration of renewable energy sources are creating both opportunities and challenges for end-users, who are increasingly expected to take an active role in energy management. However, the complexity of energy systems and the diversity of platforms and services often act as barriers to participation, making it essential to develop tools that bridge the gap between technical sophistication and everyday user experience.

EU-DREAM – Effective Uptake of Digital services to Repower European consumers and communities as Active participants in energy transition and Markets – aims to accurately reflect end-users' preferences and expectations in a simplified manner, improving customers' awareness, trust, and confidence in their interactions with the energy market by introducing a smart intermediary – as an energy attorney – for end-users. Real empowerment will come from translating all the complex details of the energy market into a simple and transparent language that relates to the user's everyday experience, like comfort, temperature, and utility bills. Citizens need to be aware of the implications of their preferences and routines associated with energy use, rather than knowing all technical details.

To make this possible, EU-DREAM embeds strong interoperability mechanisms, enabling different energy systems, platforms, and devices to seamlessly exchange and interpret data. At the core of this approach lies a semantic broker, which leverages semantic web technologies to harmonize heterogeneous data formats and models. This ensures that information from diverse sources is consistently represented, machine-readable, and meaningful. Consequently, the AI modules, analytics engines and visualization tools can deliver accurate, context-aware insights across the entire ecosystem.

Therefore, an AI-based assistant tool and an NLP-based intermediary will be created in EU-DREAM so that end-user preferences can be discussed in common layperson's language. NLP refers to the branch of artificial intelligence that enables computers to understand, interpret, and generate human language, allowing users to interact with systems conversationally rather than through complex commands.

A DT of the household will be developed based on real-time data acquired by sensors. A DT is a virtual representation of a physical system that mirrors its behavior, states, and dynamics. To qualify as a DT, it must maintain constant bidirectional communication with its real counterpart (RT) and be able to operate in simulation mode, i.e., independently from the RT, enabling simulation, analysis, and optimization.

The digital service of the household, federated into wider DTs of energy communities, is a unique tool to examine the implications for energy and flexibility markets, proposing new market design guidelines supported by novel consumer-oriented business models. Moreover, the DT can be used to test scenarios in a non-intrusive way, without affecting the functionality of the RT. The AI tool, in turn, will not only control EMS technical settings but also provide advanced algorithms to further optimize energy consumption and production.

This optimization relies on load and generation forecasting based on deep learning approaches. In parallel, the NLP interface will greatly simplify the experience of managing energy services, shielding end-users from the technical jargon (e.g., terms such as “demand response,” “frequency regulation,” or “ancillary services”) and the inherent complexity of the smart grid and the services it enables, which often act as engagement hindrances.

Digital platforms and tools will be designed and developed for both non-experienced and experienced users to significantly simplify their participation in the energy market. The solutions developed within the project will be validated in 6 living labs:

Table 1: Overview of EU-DREAM Living Labs

LL Number	Description	Location
LL1	AI-Powered Renewable Energy Communities	Coimbra, <i>PORTUGAL</i>
LL2	Energy Poverty and Vulnerable Consumers Impacts	Genk, <i>BELGIUM</i>
LL3	Energy Flexibility at Residential Scale and Interoperability	Northern Italy, <i>ITALY</i>
LL4	Consumers Empowerment for Energy Management	Dublin, <i>IRELAND</i>
LL5	Smart Energy Services for Multi-Energy Vectors	Thessaloniki, <i>GREECE</i>
LL6	DT-enabled Residential IoT Microgrid	Aalborg, <i>DENMARK</i>

Relationship with other WPs

Task 3.2 – “Interoperability for Data Sharing” – plays a pivotal role in enabling cross-WP collaboration and system-wide semantic alignment within the EU-DREAM project. Its contributions are intrinsically linked to the output and requirements of multiple work packages.

Task 3.2 interacts with the DT infrastructure, leveraging its data models and functional specifications to ensure seamless integration into the broader linked data environment. The semantic infrastructure developed within Task 3.2 is also crucial for supporting AI-based optimization modules in the DT system and for enabling data flow to energy services and consumer platforms in WP4. Additionally, the ontology-based semantic broker and linked data space created under Task 3.2 facilitate the integration of real-world Living Lab data (from WP7), ensuring interoperability across heterogeneous sources.

Additionally, Task 3.2 contributes to WP5 by ensuring that data relevant to market design and flexibility mechanisms is accessible and harmonized. Finally, a collaboration is expected, later on the project, with WP9 to ensure ethical compliance, data protection, and transparency in the handling and semantic transformation of user-related data.

Preliminaries

Before presenting the technical implementation, it is essential to establish a common understanding of the core data-related concepts that underpin EU-DREAM's architecture. The project relies on the ability to manage large, diverse, and distributed datasets from multiple pilots, integrate them seamlessly despite structural and semantic differences, and query them effectively using advanced semantic technologies. This section introduces the terminology—Big Data, Data Interoperability, Interoperability Conflicts, and Semantic Web Query Languages—that provides the conceptual framework for the project's data management and integration strategy.

Big Data

In today's data-driven landscape, massive volumes of information are being produced at accelerating rates, encompassing structured formats (e.g., relational databases with clearly defined fields), semi-structured formats (e.g., JSON, XML, or log files with flexible schemas), and unstructured formats (e.g., text or images without predefined organization). This surge in heterogeneous data—originating from sensors, digital platforms, connected devices, and user interactions—has given rise to what is commonly referred to as Big Data (1).

Broadly defined, Big Data encompasses datasets whose size, speed of generation, and complexity exceed the capabilities of conventional data processing systems. It is typically characterized by five core dimensions: Volume, Velocity, Variety, Veracity, and Value (2). Volume refers to the scale at which data accumulates, often requiring distributed storage solutions and scalable infrastructures. Velocity represents the real-time or near-real-time flow of data, which challenges the ability to ingest and process information as it arrives. Variety points to the multiplicity of data formats and sources, from structured tables to free-form text, images, and logs, making integration and interpretation more difficult. Veracity concerns the quality and trustworthiness of data, highlighting the presence of inconsistencies, ambiguity, and potential errors that can compromise analysis (1). Finally, Value represents the potential insights and benefits that can be extracted from large-scale data, provided that appropriate tools and methodologies are in place to harness it effectively. These characteristics together make Big Data a powerful but complex phenomenon, requiring advanced architectures and analytical approaches to fully exploit its potential across various sectors.

Data Interoperability

In the context of modern digital infrastructures, the growing ability to collect and store data across various enterprise systems has led to the emergence of distributed and heterogeneous data sources. These datasets, often generated independently by different departments or systems, vary in structure, semantics, and access protocols, posing a significant barrier to their combined exploitation. This challenge has elevated the importance of data interoperability, which refers to the capacity to provide unified, seamless access to decentralized, autonomous, and structurally diverse data repositories (3).

Architectures supporting data interoperability generally fall into several categories; one of them is DL, which acts as centralized repositories designed to store raw, heterogeneous data in its native formats. Unlike traditional systems that require prior transformation, a DL allows data to be ingested as-is, deferring integration, aggregation, and analysis tasks to later stages.

This approach provides significant flexibility and scalability, especially when handling diverse data models, file types, and query languages (1).

By enabling the coexistence of various storage and management technologies—such as relational databases, distributed file systems, and triple stores—DL helps break down information silos without imposing strict structural constraints upfront. An essential component of this architecture is schema governance, which supports efficient data discovery, prevents the formation of disorganized "data swamps," and ensures that users can make sense of the stored datasets.

Interoperability Conflicts across Heterogeneous Data Sources

Achieving semantic interoperability across heterogeneous data sources poses significant challenges, particularly due to a wide range of potential conflicts arising from differences in structure, semantics, and context.

One fundamental issue is the structuredness conflict, which appears when data sources vary in their degree of formalization—ranging from structured data (e.g., relational databases with fixed schemas), to semi-structured formats (e.g., RDF or XML), to unstructured content (e.g., text, images, or other multimedia) that lacks a predefined schema. Schematic conflicts occur when similar concepts are modelled inconsistently across datasets, involving variations in attributes, structural hierarchies (e.g., class vs. property), data types, naming conventions, or even ontology usage (4).

Another common issue is the domain conflict, which emerges from different interpretations of the same domain, such as synonyms, homonyms, acronyms, or differing semantic constraints applied to concept definitions (4). Representation conflicts reflect inconsistencies in how the same values are expressed—through different units, levels of precision, identifiers, or encoding formats—while language conflicts arise when data or metadata is presented in different natural languages (4). Finally, granularity conflicts stem from discrepancies in the level of detail or temporal resolution at which data is captured, such as differing aggregation methods or sampling frequencies (4).

Identifying and resolving these semantic interoperability conflicts is a critical step toward enabling coherent data integration and unlocking the full analytical value of complex, distributed data ecosystems.

Introduction to Semantic Web, Ontologies and Query Languages

The Semantic Web provides a formal framework for representing, integrating, and querying distributed data using standardized technologies. At its core is Resource Description Framework (RDF), a graph-based model that encodes data as subject–predicate–object triples, collectively forming RDF graphs and datasets. Resources are identified using IRIs or blank nodes, while literals support datatypes and language tags according to RDF specifications.

Ontologies are formal representations of concepts within a domain and the relationships between them. They define a shared vocabulary and set of rules to describe entities, properties, hierarchies, and constraints (5). Ontologies play a crucial role in enabling semantic interoperability, allowing heterogeneous datasets to be integrated and queried consistently.

By enriching raw data with semantic meaning, ontologies support reasoning, advanced analytics, and the discovery of insights that are often difficult to extract from traditional tabular datasets (1). Knowledge graphs, in particular, leverage ontologies to organize information as interconnected nodes and edges, facilitating intuitive querying and a deeper understanding of complex data.

To ensure semantic interoperability, schema languages such as RDFS and OWL enable the definition of vocabularies, class hierarchies, and logical constraints. RDF data can be accessed through SPARQL endpoints using the SPARQL Protocol. SPARQL, a W3C-recommended graph query language, supports pattern-based queries over RDF graphs, including basic graph patterns (BGPs), joins, unions, filters, and modifiers like DISTINCT, GROUP BY, ORDER BY, and LIMIT. Queries can return Boolean answers (ASK), variable bindings (SELECT), constructed triples (CONSTRUCT), or resource descriptions (DESCRIBE).

In parallel, the property graph model provides an alternative way to represent graph data, where nodes and edges can carry arbitrary key-value properties. Cypher, the native query language for Neo4j and other property graph databases, is optimized for traversing and matching patterns in property graphs. Cypher queries express graph patterns using an intuitive ASCII-art syntax (e.g., (n:Person)-[:KNOWS]->(m)) and support operations such as MATCH, WHERE, RETURN, and aggregations. Unlike SPARQL, rooted in triple patterns, Cypher allows more expressive navigation of deeply nested relationships, particularly in knowledge graphs modelled as property graphs.

By combining RDF, ontologies, and graph query languages, heterogeneous datasets can be semantically integrated into unified knowledge graphs, unlocking richer insights, enabling intelligent analytics, and supporting complex reasoning across diverse data sources.

EU-DREAM Data Sources

Pilot overview and available Data Sources

As part of the project, each Living Lab was requested to provide a detailed document outlining the technical specifications and metadata related to their respective use cases. This initiative aims to facilitate the understanding, comparison, and eventual integration of diverse datasets into the broader data architecture of the system. By harmonizing and analysing these specifications, the project seeks to ensure seamless interoperability across Living Labs and to support robust analytics on energy consumption and device monitoring.

Each Living Lab may contribute datasets with varying coverage, potentially including overall energy consumption and generation, device-level monitoring in terms of instantaneous active/reactive power consumption, and environmental context data. Depending on availability, these datasets can comprise historical records, real-time measurements, and forecast models. Forecast models can, for instance, be derived from historical consumption and generation patterns using statistical methods or machine learning techniques, or provided directly by external forecasting services. This allows the datasets not only to reflect past and present states but also to anticipate future energy demand and supply, thereby providing a flexible foundation for energy analytics.

Dataset Overview by Living Lab

Living Lab 1 (LL1) focuses on household-level energy consumption data, i.e., measurements aggregated at the level of individual residential units, collected at 15-minute intervals. The dataset is accessible via the Cleanwatts API and primarily stored in JSON format. Data volume varies per household, with storage managed on the LL's proprietary platform. The data are structured as a time series, meaning that each record is indexed by a timestamp and provides a chronological sequence of consumption values, which enables trend analysis, load profiling, and forecasting.

Living Lab 2 (LL2) is expected to provide high-resolution monitoring of household energy and environmental parameters, capturing over 200 measurements per household at one-minute intervals. This includes electricity consumption, appliance-level activity, indoor temperature and humidity, and other contextual variables. Data, formatted as CSV files, may range from 600 MB to 3 GB per household per month. Availability was planned for February 2025; however, the exact contribution and coverage from LL2 remain uncertain. Access to the data, if provided, will be facilitated via the SmarThor API¹ and an accompanying web interface.

Living Lab 3 (LL3) offers device-level consumption data, tariff information, and environmental forecasts generated from predictive models. This dataset includes both historical and real-time consumption recorded at intervals between one and fifteen minutes, with tariff and forecast data aggregated hourly. Data are delivered in JSON and CSV formats. Currently, data availability is partial, pending full deployment. Storage is maintained on the EU-DREAM cloud platform. Expected outputs include timeline visualizations.

¹ SmarThor API official website: <https://www.openthor.be/en/projects/smarthor>

Living Lab 4 (LL4) provides sparse consumption metadata, including summary information about energy use such as total consumption per device, timestamps of measurements, and basic operational status indicators, sampled at one-minute intervals. These data, stored in TXT format, are not currently accessible to external users; however, partial integration into the EU-DREAM edge infrastructure may allow aggregated access or analysis at the platform level in the future. Storage occurs locally on edge SSD devices (500 GB). Output formats and applications remain undefined.

Living Lab 5 (LL5) encompasses comprehensive device-level data, including real-time and historical measurements of individual devices' power consumption, voltage, current, and operational status, as well as calculated energy savings metrics. Sampling frequency ranges from 30 seconds to one hour. Data are primarily JSON-formatted and range in size on the order of megabytes per dataset. Availability varies: some datasets are fully accessible to EU-DREAM partners, while others remain restricted to the contributing labs. Access is provided via RESTful APIs. Storage is distributed between the Living Labs' platforms and the EU-DREAM cloud environment. The deliverables include bar and line charts, detailed reports, and real-time alerts.

Living Lab 6 (LL6) features high-frequency household-level and device-level active and reactive power consumption/generation, and also local weather data with a granularity of five seconds, covering the period from 2018 to the present. Data formats include JSON, CSV, and XLSX. Data volume is substantial, though exact metrics are unspecified. Data access is API-based. The data is acquired and stored locally, but it is available to the EU-DREAM partners upon request.

The data collection efforts across the six Living Labs exhibit considerable heterogeneity in terms of temporal resolution, accessibility, and developmental maturity. While some cases offer well-structured and accessible data pipelines, others remain under development or subject to access constraints. This diversity provides a robust foundation for advanced energy data analytics, but would benefit from enhanced metadata standardization and the development of unified ontologies to facilitate cross-dataset integration and broader interoperability.

The following table summarizes the key characteristics of the datasets collected across the six Living Labs:

Living Lab	Data Type	Sampling Frequency	Formats	Approximate Volume	Access / Storage	Availability / Status
LL1	Dwelling-level energy consumption	15 minutes	JSON	Variable per dwelling	Cleanwatts API, proprietary platform	Available
LL2	High-resolution household monitoring	1 minute	CSV	600 MB – 3 GB per month	SmarThor API, web interface	Available from February 2025
LL3	Device-level consumption, tariffs, forecasts	1–15 minutes (consumption), hourly (tariffs, forecasts)	JSON, CSV	Partial	EU-DREAM cloud platform	Partially available, deployment ongoing
LL4	Sparse consumption metadata	1 minute	TXT	N/A	Local edge SSD (500 GB)	Not externally accessible
LL5	Comprehensive device data (consumption, savings)	30 seconds – 1 hour	JSON	Megabytes per dataset	RESTful APIs, Living Labs platforms and EU-DREAM cloud	Partially available
LL6	High-frequency energy consumption	5 seconds	JSON, CSV, XLSX	Large (unspecified)	API	Available

Figure 1: characteristics of the datasets collected across EU-DREAM Living Labs

The Dynamic District Management Server

The Dynamic District Management Server (DDIM) Server is a core component of the EU-DREAM project, designed to support advanced energy analytics and semantic data integration within urban Living Labs.

The DDIM Server was developed by Dublin City University (DCU), a research university located in Dublin, Ireland, well known for its commitment to technological innovation and applied research, particularly in the fields of energy, environment, and information technology. DCU had previously collaborated with the AKKO team on another research project, where the DDIM Server was already deployed. This prior experience inspired its reuse within the framework of the EU-DREAM project. As a result, the DDIM Server remains a research-focused tool, not commercially available, and is still under active development and improvement. Since it was not developed by the AKKO team, some functionalities are still being explored, understood, and refined by the project partners.

Technically, the DDIM Server is a Django/Neo4J-based platform that enables front-end applications to build unified knowledge graphs from diverse data sources, including CSV files, existing graphs, and other formats. It offers an API that guides users through the process of uploading data and establishing semantic relationships. By leveraging ontologies, the server creates entities and links them meaningfully, supporting interoperability and semantic integration across heterogeneous datasets (5).

Architectural Description

The architecture below (Figure 1) illustrates how the EU-DREAM system manages semantic data integration. The DDIM-Server sends a query to the Data Platform. The query is then processed by a FastAPI² and directed to either MongoDB or InfluxDB, depending on the data type. In this setup, MongoDB stores heterogeneous, document-oriented data such as metadata, device descriptions, and configuration files, while InfluxDB is optimized for high-frequency time-series data, including energy consumption and production measurements. Once the appropriate database executes the query and returns the data, it is sent back to the DDIM-Server. This data is then parsed and enriched through a semantic broker before being saved in the graph database and metadata storage.

Although this represents the current working architecture, it remains subject to modification as the project progresses. Adjustments may be required not only based on the ongoing development of Task T3.2, but also to accommodate requirements arising from other related tasks, ensuring that the system remains flexible and responsive to evolving needs.

² FastAPI official website: <https://fastapi.tiangolo.com/>.

Figure 2: Architecture of the DDIM Server and The Data Platform

Internally, the DDIM system relies on several tightly integrated components to deliver its semantic capabilities.

At its core, the Neo4j graph database serves as the graph-based storage engine, enabling the structured representation of entities and their relationships. It plays a critical role in semantic enrichment, storing ontological relationships, supporting SPARQL-like queries (via extensions), enabling reasoning and inference, and allowing visual exploration of the knowledge graph. This infrastructure forms the backbone of contextual reasoning and semantic linking across domains.

Semantic integration is orchestrated by the Semantic Broker, which acts as an intermediary layer between raw data and the formal ontology model—based on SAREF. The broker maps heterogeneous inputs to a unified semantic layer, ensures consistent data interpretation across domains, and facilitates ontology-based data alignment. It also supports federated queries and enables interoperability between components by maintaining a coherent semantic model throughout the platform.

To enable structured communication with external platforms and internal modules, the system exposes a RESTful API. This HTTP-based service access layer provides secure and standardized endpoints for data ingestion and distribution, supports integration with third-party systems, and facilitates a decoupled architecture. Authentication and authorization are managed through Keycloak, ensuring secure access control.

The server also contains a metadata storage buffer, used to temporarily store incoming unstructured or semi-structured datasets before semantic transformation. This component acts as a decoupling layer between ingestion and processing, ensuring data integrity and availability for transformation workflows handled by the Semantic Broker.

Finally, ontology-instance linking is handled through a set of predefined semantic rules—such as INSTANCE_OF, MEASURES_PROPERTY, and PRODUCES—which establish formal relationships between raw data elements and ontology classes. This ensures semantic consistency throughout the knowledge graph and supports advanced querying, reasoning, and cross-domain integration within the CDS.

Technical implementation details

The DDIM Server implementation reveals several concrete design choices that complement its architectural role within the broader platform. At its foundation, the system is built on Django, with the Django REST Framework (DRF) enabling the definition of endpoints and request handling. Supporting libraries include `django-bootstrap4` for template rendering and `django-cors-headers`, which facilitates cross-domain communication during development and integration phases.

The configuration also highlights the dual persistence strategy: while Neo4j acts as the semantic backbone for graph storage and reasoning, a MySQL database is used as a relational store for metadata and auxiliary artifacts. The Django ORM (Object-Relational Mapper) ensures smooth interaction with the relational layer.

Two custom Django applications structure the server's internal logic:

- **graphcreate** – responsible for constructing graph entities from ingested datasets.
- **querygraph** – handling querying and retrieval of semantic data from Neo4j.

The middleware stack integrates standard Django security modules (session, authentication, messaging), ensuring controlled communication between the server and external clients.

Static and media content are managed through a consolidated directory structure (`/staticfiles` for static assets, `/static/` for media), enabling consistent deployment both in development and production. This approach simplifies development by allowing developers to reference assets from a predictable path, while in production, it facilitates integration with content delivery networks (CDNs) or reverse proxies. As a result, the same configuration can be reliably applied across environments, reducing deployment errors and ensuring that assets are served efficiently.

Endpoint routing and modular design

The server's URL configuration reflects a deliberately modular design. Instead of consolidating all functionality into a single, monolithic layer—where all components and services are tightly coupled and managed together—responsibilities are distributed across application-specific modules. This approach improves maintainability, scalability, and flexibility, allowing individual modules to be developed, updated, or replaced independently.

The `graphcreate` module is exposed at the `/create/` endpoint, enabling users to ingest and transform raw datasets into semantic graphs. Each module manages its own routes and logic independently, supporting maintainability and future extensions.

Static and media files are served from centralized locations defined in the configuration. While this approach works in development, production environments typically offload static content to a dedicated web server (e.g., NGINX or Apache) for improved performance and scalability.

This modular design facilitates adding new functionality, such as additional data processing pipelines, visualization modules, or external service connectors, without impacting existing components. It also maintains a clear separation of responsibilities, allowing ingestion and querying services to evolve independently.

REST Endpoints for Data Ingestion and Graph Construction

The DDIM Server implements its REST API layer using Django REST Framework. Each service endpoint extends the *APIView* base, ensuring a consistent request/response cycle. Together, these endpoints orchestrate the end-to-end workflow:

- **Graph initialization services** configure the Neo4j environment, enforce constraints, and import RDF/TTL files into the graph database.
- **File ingestion services** handle the upload of raw CSV datasets, extract column metadata, and generate Cypher commands that create semantic nodes in Neo4j.
- **Metadata management services** expose information about uploaded files, their schema, and their relationships with other entities.
- **Rule creation services** allow users to define semantic links (e.g., *contains*, *equalTo*, *isa*, *has*) across datasets by dynamically generating and executing Cypher queries.
- **Object-level endpoints** provide fine-grained access to specific files, metadata, or rules, enabling retrieval, update tracking, and deletion when supported.

This modular API design ensures that data ingestion, semantic enrichment, and ontology-driven linking can be performed incrementally, while maintaining a coherent workflow across all services.

DDIM Server Data Model

The server's data model supports a modular pipeline for ingesting raw datasets, extracting metadata, and generating semantic graphs.

1. **Entity and Relationship Catalogs:** two models maintain centralized vocabularies of entity names and relationship types. These ensure that nodes and edges in the graph are consistently named, supporting semantic integrity across the platform.
2. **File Uploads:** raw datasets are captured through an uploaded files interface, which tracks both the file contents and descriptive metadata (e.g., filename, description, associated entity, and upload time). This provides a structured entry point into the pipeline, ensuring all incoming data is logged and traceable.
3. **Metadata Extraction:** uploaded files are analysed to capture structural information such as column names. This metadata guides downstream processes, indicating how individual fields map to nodes and edges in the semantic graph.
4. **Graph Construction Rules:** the system allows users or processes to define rules for connecting datasets, specifying how columns in different files relate. Each rule identifies the type of relationship and the relevant fields from the source files, enabling automated generation of graph relationships in Neo4j.
5. **Pipeline Flow:** Users upload raw datasets → the system extracts metadata → semantic nodes are created using the entity catalog → relationships are established according to defined rules. This separation of responsibilities ensures modularity, traceability, and extensibility, allowing new datasets or relationship types to be integrated without disrupting existing workflows.

Data Serialization Layer

The server uses a serialization layer to translate between the internal data models and external representations used in APIs. This layer ensures that data can flow seamlessly between clients (e.g., web interfaces or external services) and the backend.

Serializers act as an interface between Python objects (models) and JSON or other formats used in REST APIs. They allow uploaded files, extracted metadata, and graph rules to be sent to clients, received from clients, and validated consistently (8).

Serialized Models

- **UploadedFiles:** the complete dataset of uploaded files can be exposed or accepted via the API, including file content, description, associated entity, and upload timestamp.
- **FileMetadata:** metadata associated with each uploaded file, such as column names, is serialized to support downstream processing or client-side display.
- **CreateRule:** rules defining how datasets are linked in the graph are also serialized, enabling the API to create, update, or retrieve relationship mappings.

By mapping models to a serialized format automatically, this layer decouples internal database representation from external communication, allowing the platform to evolve its internal models without impacting API consumers.

This approach supports modularity, consistent data validation, and clean integration with front-end applications or external services.

Connection with other components

Communication with the Common Data Space

The table below outlines the key mechanisms enabling communication between the DDIM Server and the Common Data Space. It highlights the technologies used for data access, semantic querying, and storage, as well as the integration with both graph and time-series databases to ensure efficient and interoperable data exchange:

Table 2: Communication of the DDIM Server with the common Data Space

Name	Description
<i>REST API for data access</i>	The DDIM Server exposes a REST API to query enriched and linked data
<i>SPARQL Query Support</i>	The DDIM Server provides a SPARQL endpoint, allowing queries on linked data
<i>Linked Data Storage</i>	Data imported by the DDIM Server is stored using a unified ontology to ensure interoperability
<i>Neo4j Connectivity</i>	The DDIM Server integrates with a Neo4j database to manage entity relationships
<i>InfluxDB Connectivity</i>	The DDIM Server retrieves and stores time-series data in InfluxDB for dynamic data analysis

Integration with IMC Connectors

The following table presents the main integration features between the DDIM Server and IMC Connectors. It summarizes how various data sources are ingested, processed, and semantically aligned, as well as how data traceability is maintained throughout the system:

Table 3: Integration of DDIM Server with IMC Connectors

Name	Description
Data ingestion via REST API	external databases, and BIM models are received via REST API
File ingestion via SFTP	The DDIM Server ingests CSV, JSON, and BIM files transferred through a secure SFTP server
Source registration in the ontology	Received data is transformed and stored in the semantic graph to ensure consistency
Data history and update tracking	The DDIM Server maintains a history of data updates and logs changes for traceability

Communication with the Digital Twin and Other Modules

The table below outlines the main communication mechanisms between the DDIM Server, the Digital Twin, and other system modules. It highlights the technologies used for querying, data exchange, and ensuring secure interactions within the platform:

Table 4: Communication of DDIM Server with DT and others

Name	Description
GraphQL API for querying	A GraphQL API is provided to query DDIM Server data
Query results published via MQTT	Query results are sent via an MQTT broker, to which the DT can subscribe to
Secure communication	All communications between the DDIM Server and the DT are authenticated via Keycloak and encrypted

User Guide

Data Sources Integration

One of the initial steps in the data integration process involves preparing the dataset for semantic alignment and interoperability. This preparation phase includes normalizing the data to ensure consistency, completeness, and cleanliness across all sources. Here, "cleanliness" refers to ensuring the data are free from errors, inconsistencies, duplicates, and missing or invalid entries, so that the datasets are accurate, reliable, and ready for subsequent analysis.

By harmonizing formats, resolving inconsistencies, and addressing missing or duplicated values, data normalization lays the foundation for effective mapping to external ontologies or integration into a unified schema.

Without this critical step, subsequent integration efforts—such as schema matching, entity alignment, and semantic enrichment—may be hindered by structural discrepancies or ambiguous data representations. Thus, data preparation plays a pivotal role in enabling reliable, coherent integration of heterogeneous data sources.

Ontologies Integration

Integrating existing ontologies into a data project to enrich and organize information requires a structured process that ensures semantic alignment and interoperability — “enriching information” means adding meaningful semantic details (such as metadata, relationships, and standardized categories) to make the data more informative and easier to analyse.

The first step involves a thorough analysis and understanding of the selected ontologies. This includes identifying the most relevant ontologies and examining their structures, such as classes, properties, relationships, and controlled vocabularies. It is crucial to assess whether these ontologies are compatible with the project’s data and whether they can effectively enhance or organize the information.

For the EU-DREAM project, the SAREF ontology³ (version 3.2.1) was chosen to ensure alignment with European standards (7), promoting consistency and facilitating future integration with other semantic resources and platforms.

SAREF ontology is a standardized framework developed by the ETSI to enable interoperability among various IoT solutions across different sectors. Its primary goal is to facilitate a common understanding of smart devices and their functions, promoting seamless communication and integration between diverse systems (5).

At its core, SAREF focuses on the concept of a Device, defined as a tangible object designed to accomplish specific tasks in environments such as households, public buildings, or offices. Each device performs one or more Functions to achieve its intended tasks. For instance, a washing machine, as an example of a controllable type (Device), is designed to wash clothes (Task) and performs functions like start and stop operations.

Devices can have properties that uniquely characterize them, such as model and manufacturer details. They can also be associated with Commodities (e.g., water, gas) and can measure specific Properties like temperature, energy, or smoke levels. Furthermore, devices may consist of other devices, allowing for complex assemblies and hierarchies. Devices can be either controllable, meaning their operation can be remotely managed or scheduled (e.g., washing machines, dishwashers), or non-controllable, operating autonomously without external intervention (e.g., refrigerators, freezers).

To cater to the diverse needs of various domains, SAREF has been extended into multiple verticals, each addressing specific sector requirements (5):

- **SAREF4ENER:** Focuses on the energy domain, detailing concepts related to energy measurement, management, and optimization.
- **SAREF4ENVI:** Targets the environmental domain, encompassing aspects like environmental monitoring and assessment.

³ Energy Vocabulary Hub: <https://energy.vocabulary-hub.eu/>

- **SAREF4BLDG:** Pertains to the building domain, covering building automation, control systems, and related infrastructure.
- **SAREF4CITY:** Addresses the smart cities domain, including urban infrastructure, services, and citizen engagement.
- **SAREF4INMA:** Relates to industry and manufacturing, focusing on industrial processes, machinery, and production systems.
- **SAREF4AGRI:** Covers the smart agriculture and food chain domains, dealing with farming practices, livestock management, and food distribution.
- **SAREF4AUTO:** Concerns the automotive domain, involving vehicle systems, transportation, and mobility solutions.
- **SAREF4WEAR:** Pertains to the wearable's domain, including wearable technology and personal devices.
- **SAREF4WATR:** Relates to the water domain, covering water management, distribution, and quality monitoring.
- **SAREF4LIFT:** Addresses the smart lifts domain, focusing on elevator systems and their integration into building management.
- **SAREF4GRID:** Concerns the smart grid domain, dealing with electricity networks, grid management, and related technologies.

These extensions ensure that SAREF remains relevant and applicable across a wide range of industries, promoting interoperability and standardization in the IoT landscape.

Once appropriate ontologies are selected, the next phase involves mapping dataset attributes to the corresponding concepts in the ontology.

Alignment of Data with Ontological Concepts

Following the normalization and preparation of datasets, a critical phase in the data integration workflow is the alignment of local data elements with the reference ontology concepts previously introduced (in this case, SAREF). This step ensures semantic consistency by linking dataset attributes—such as sensor readings, device identifiers, or consumption metrics—to standardized ontology classes and properties.

Key ontology concepts aligned include:

- *saref:Device* — representing physical or virtual devices (e.g., smart meters, thermostats)
- *saref:EnergyConsumption* — capturing energy usage metrics
- *saref:Temperature* — for environmental or device temperature readings
- *saref:Measurement* — representing individual data points or observations
- *saref:Command* — corresponding to control instructions or operational states

General Alignment Pipeline

- **Data Normalization and Preprocessing** : raw datasets from Living Labs are initially cleaned and converted into standardized formats (e.g., CSV, JSON) with uniform naming conventions and timestamp formats. This step addresses missing values, removes duplicates, and converts units when necessary to ensure consistency.
- **Candidate Concept Identification** : each dataset attribute (e.g., column names, JSON keys) is compared against ontology vocabularies. Automated tools or scripts extract potential candidate concepts by matching labels, synonyms, or abbreviations to SAREF classes and properties. For example, a column named “temp” or “temperature” would be matched to *saref:Temperature*.
- **Disambiguation and Contextual Validation**: when multiple ontology concepts could correspond to a single data element, contextual information is leveraged to resolve ambiguities. This can include metadata about the data source, device type, or domain-specific constraints. Reasoning engines or human expert input validate and finalize the correct mapping.
- **Semantic Annotation**: the data is then enriched with semantic metadata by generating RDF triples that explicitly link data elements to ontology concepts.
- **Integration and Storage**: the annotated datasets are stored within semantic databases (triple stores or graph databases) compatible with Semantic Web standards. This enables querying via SPARQL and CYPHER endpoints, integration with other datasets, and application of ontology-driven reasoning to infer new knowledge or detect inconsistencies.
- **Continuous Refinement**: the alignment process is iterative: as new data sources or Living Labs come online, mappings are updated and refined. Feedback loops from data users and domain experts ensure evolving accuracy and completeness of semantic annotations.

This pipeline supports coherent integration of heterogeneous data from the various Living Labs, facilitating interoperability and enabling advanced analytics based on unified semantic representations.

User Interactions and accessibility

A key objective of the EU-DREAM platform is to provide end-users with an intuitive and accessible interface to interact with complex energy data and services. The system is designed to bridge the gap between technical energy management functionalities and everyday user experience, ensuring that all users—regardless of their technical background—can engage effectively with the platform.

User Interaction Features

- **Natural Language Interface**

Leveraging NLP, the platform offers a conversational assistant that allows users to query and control their energy consumption using everyday language. This approach lowers the barrier to entry and enhances user engagement by avoiding complex technical language.

- **Knowledge Graph Visualization and Analysis**

Knowledge graphs provide significant advantages for analysing and monitoring energy systems. By structuring data semantically, they enable efficient querying without relying on complex SQL joins. For example, in the case of the LL6 wind turbine dataset, which contains the turbine’s status and active power, users can visualize a full day of turbine activity. Operators can also identify precise connection and disconnection periods, monitor performance, and ensure adherence to operational schedules.

Beyond basic visualization, knowledge graphs support pattern and trend analysis, detection of anomalies such as zero output during active periods, and monitoring of unexpected shutdowns. They also reveal relationships between variables, such as how active power evolves after the turbine is switched on. In the case of LL6 wind turbines, power output depends primarily on wind speed and the turbine’s connection to the grid, rather than on environmental factors like temperature or humidity.

Integration with AI and predictive analytics further enhances operational management by forecasting future energy output, anticipating potential failures, and enabling pre-emptive maintenance. Real-time monitoring of continuously updated measurements can furthermore allow immediate detection of anomalies and triggering of alerts, minimizing unplanned downtime and improving overall system reliability.

Continuing with the LL6 wind turbine dataset, we can illustrate how the data is structured and visualized in a knowledge graph:

Figure 3- Fragment of the LL6 wind turbine KG with a sample Cypher query

Executing a query in Neo4j produces a graph where the wind turbine (beige), its measurements (pink), and timestamps (green) are displayed, with relationships such as "HAS_MEASUREMENT" and "RECORDED_AT".

The corresponding raw JSON data provides detailed information on each node and relationship:

	a	a_labels	a_properties	r	b	b_labels	b_properties	r2
1	<pre>{ "identity": 2, "labels": ["WindTurbine"], "properties": { "id": "LL6", "elementId": "4:0dc01ac6-8b23-4c59-84c2-0cf91f426e7a:2" } }</pre>	["WindTurbine"]	<pre>{ "id": "LL6" }</pre>	<pre>{ "identity": 54, "start": 2, "end": 56, "type": "HAS_MEASUREMENT", "properties": { "elementId": "5:0dc01ac6-8b23-4c59-84c2-0cf91f426e7a:54", "startNodeElementId": "4:0dc01ac6-8b23-4c59-84c2-0cf91f426e7a:2" } }</pre>	<pre>{ "identity": 56, "labels": ["Measurement"], "properties": { "elementId": "4:0dc01ac6-8b23-4c59-84c2-0cf91f426e7a:56" } }</pre>	["Measurement"]	<pre>{ "identity": 55, "start": 56, "end": 55, "type": "RECORDED_AT", "properties": { "elementId": "5:0dc01ac6-8b23-4c59-84c2-0cf91f426e7a:55", "startNodeElementId": "4:0dc01ac6-8b23-4c59-84c2-0cf91f426e7a:2" } }</pre>	<pre>{ "identity": 55, "start": 56, "end": 55, "type": "RECORDED_AT", "properties": { "elementId": "5:0dc01ac6-8b23-4c59-84c2-0cf91f426e7a:55", "startNodeElementId": "4:0dc01ac6-8b23-4c59-84c2-0cf91f426e7a:2" } }</pre>

Figure 4- JSON representation of the LL6 wind turbine KG fragment

A broader view of the graph illustrates how the turbine (beige) connects to multiple measurements (pink) and timestamps (green):

Figure 5: Extract of LL6 wind turbine KG

This structured representation enhances data navigation and analysis, providing a foundation for advanced operations, including pattern detection, trend analysis, predictive maintenance, and real-time monitoring.

Building once again on the previous example of the LL6 wind turbine dataset, we can now illustrate the impact of integrating the SAREF ontology into the DDIM Server. Following this semantic enrichment, the knowledge graph becomes significantly richer, with numerous additional nodes and relationships. For example :

- **Entities linked to SAREF classes:** measurements and devices are associated with standardized ontology classes
- **New semantic relationships:** e.g., a Wind Turbine PRODUCES Energy, or a Measurement MEASURES_PROPERTY Power
- **Improved interoperability:** data can now be queried in a uniform, semantically consistent manner

Figure 6: extract of LL6 wind turbine KG enriched with SAREF

While the visualization displays only a portion of the full graph, it effectively demonstrates how ontology-based enrichment adds new layers of information.

A closer view highlights specific examples of the additional details introduced by SAREF, providing a tangible illustration of how semantic connections enhance the original dataset:

Figure 7: Fragment of the enriched LL6 wind turbine KG with a sample Cypher query

Figure 8: JSON representation of the enriched LL6 wind turbine KG fragment

This enrichment is not limited to the current scope; the system allows the definition of further links between dataset elements and SAREF concepts, enabling flexible and deeper semantic modelling according to project requirements.

Automated Knowledge Graph Generation

The most recent task addressed in the project, which is still under active development, concerns the automation of knowledge graph creation.

Automating this process is essential because manual construction of knowledge graphs is time-consuming, error-prone, and does not scale well when dealing with large or heterogeneous datasets. By automating it, the project ensures faster integration of new data sources, higher consistency, and improved scalability of the data platform.

The aim is to design a pipeline capable of transforming raw data into structured RDF graphs that comply with the SAREF ontology. This work is key to enabling semantic interoperability and ensuring that heterogeneous data sources can be seamlessly integrated into the project's data platform.

At a high level, the pipeline follows several steps (see accompanying diagram):

- **Ontology extraction:** The SAREF ontology is parsed and indexed to provide the common semantic framework.
- **Data preparation:** At the moment, we are only experimenting with CSV files: they are processed, identifiers and types are automatically detected, and values are normalized to facilitate integration.
- **Semantic matching:** Dataset content is aligned with the most relevant SAREF classes and properties. This step allows the system to interpret raw columns and values in light of the ontology.
- **LLM processing:** An LLM generates RDF triples in Turtle syntax. This generative component makes the system more flexible, as it can handle variations in data format and terminology without extensive manual configuration.
- **Knowledge graph building:** The triples are validated, aggregated, and integrated into a single RDF graph. In this step, consistency is checked, and only the correct namespaces and datatypes are retained.
- **Export:** The final output is serialized into a .ttl file, which can be ingested by the DDIM Server and the wider data platform (the latter still being a work in progress).

Figure 9: Knowledge Graph Generation Pipeline

This task combines symbolic methods (ontology parsing, semantic similarity, rule-based triple building) with generative AI (LLM-based triple generation). The result is a hybrid approach that is both robust and adaptable, capable of dealing with different data sources while ensuring alignment with project standards.

Next Steps

The development of the automated knowledge graph generation pipeline is still ongoing, and several important actions are planned in the coming months.

The immediate priority will be the refinement and further development of the current script, in order to improve its efficiency and extend its capabilities for handling diverse data sources. In parallel, systematic testing will be carried out to ensure the robustness of the approach and to verify the correctness of the RDF triples produced by the pipeline.

Once these foundations are consolidated, the next milestone will be the integration of the script and the automatically generated knowledge graphs into the DDIM Server. At this stage, the final output will be ingested not only by the DDIM Server but also by the wider data platform, which is itself still under development.

Ultimately, the deployment of the full data platform will mark the completion of this process, with the automated pipeline serving as a core component for scalable and semantically consistent data management.

Conclusion

The integration of heterogeneous data sources into semantically enriched knowledge graphs presents both a technical and conceptual challenge in the context of Big Data and distributed digital ecosystems. Through the use of standardized ontologies such as SAREF, supported by semantic web technologies like RDF, SPARQL, and graph-based storage systems, the EU-DREAM platform—exemplified by the DDIM Server—demonstrates a scalable approach to achieving semantic interoperability. The system's architecture facilitates data ingestion, normalization, alignment with domain-specific ontologies, and secure, standards-compliant communication with other modules such as the Digital Twin and the Common Data Space. As a result, it enables consistent data modelling, historical tracking, and dynamic querying across diverse domains and formats.

Nevertheless, while the current implementation addresses many interoperability and integration concerns, several directions for future work remain. These include enhancing automated ontology matching techniques to minimize manual intervention during data alignment and incorporating machine learning models for entity resolution and semantic disambiguation.

Another promising avenue lies in improving multilingual interoperability to support cross-border use cases within European data spaces. Furthermore, efforts can be made to integrate additional domain-specific ontologies, expand compatibility with emerging data governance frameworks, and establish dynamic feedback loops from downstream applications (e.g., predictive models in the Digital Twin) to continuously refine semantic mappings.

Finally, a key ongoing effort is the automation of knowledge graph generation, which transforms raw data into ontology-compliant RDF graphs with minimal manual intervention. This development is critical for accelerating data integration, ensuring consistency, and supporting scalable semantic management across the EU-DREAM platform.

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Annexes

Configuration of DDIM Server

This annex provides step-by-step instructions to configure the environment, build Docker containers, initialize the database, and create a knowledge graph using uploaded CSV files.

1. Prerequisites

Ensure the following are installed on your system:

- Docker
 - Python
 - Terminal application (command-line access)
-

2. Clone the DDIM Repository

1. Open a terminal window.
 2. Clone the repository from GitHub or GitLab: `git clone <repository_url>`
 3. Ensure a `.env.dev` file exists in the project's root directory for environment-specific settings required during the build.
-

3. Configure Neo4j Settings

1. Open `settings.py` in the project directory.
 2. Set up database credentials for Neo4j (IP, username, password, etc.) to enable data connections.
-

4. Build and Start Docker Containers

1. Navigate to the folder containing `docker-compose.yml`.
2. Run the following commands:

```
docker compose build
```

```
docker compose up
```

This will build and start all services required for the DDIM server.

5. Disable Neo4j Authentication

1. Open the Neo4j container in Docker Desktop (or other deployment method).
 2. Navigate to `/var/lib/neo4j/conf`.
 3. Edit the configuration file: `dbms.security.auth_enabled=false`
 4. Restart the Neo4j container to apply the change.
-

6. Run Database Migrations and Collect Static Files

1. Open a terminal in the web container.
 2. Execute Django's migration commands to set up and migrate the project's database schema.
-

7. Data Upload and Knowledge Graph Creation

7.1 Upload CSV Files

1. CSV files are uploaded to the server and parsed. Column headers are recorded.
 2. This process enables three main purposes:
 - **Knowledge Discovery:** Identify data sources and describe attributes.
 - **Graph Creation:** Connect entities according to the ontology.
 - **Data Representation:** Neo4j executes LOAD, CREATE, and MERGE commands to represent the data in the graph. Each CSV row corresponds to a new entity.
-

7.2 Running Neo4j

- **Web Browser:** `http://172.30.16.28:7475/browser/`
 - **Inside Docker Container:**

```
docker exec -it <neo4j_container_name> bin/cypher-shell -u neo4j -p <password>
```
 - **From Outside Docker** (if Bolt port 7687 exposed):

```
cypher-shell -a bolt://localhost:7687 -u neo4j -p mypassword
```
-

7.3 Load CSV Data in Docker

1. Copy CSV file into the container:

```
docker cp <csv_file_name> neo4j:/var/lib/neo4j/import/
```
2. Execute in cypher-shell:

```
LOAD CSV WITH HEADERS FROM 'file:///<csv_file_name>' AS row
RETURN row;
```

7.4 Retrieve Column Names

```
LOAD CSV WITH HEADERS FROM 'file:///<csv_file_name>' AS row
RETURN keys(row) AS headers
LIMIT 1;
```

- keys(row) returns a list of column names.
- LIMIT 1 ensures only one result.

Note: Neo4j re-reads the CSV from the import folder; the query does not modify the graph.

Tutorial: Linking LL6 Data to the SAREF Ontology

Prerequisites

- LL6 data loaded into Neo4j (measurements, timestamps, devices).
 - SAREF ontology integrated as a subgraph with proper IRIs (e.g., saref:Power, saref:Measurement).
-

Step 1: Link LL6 Instances to SAREF Classes

```
MATCH (inst:Measurement)
MATCH (cls:Entity {id: "saref:Measurement"})
MERGE (inst)-[:INSTANCE_OF]->(cls);
```

```
MATCH (inst:TimeStamp)
MATCH (cls:Entity {id: "saref:Time"})
MERGE (inst)-[:INSTANCE_OF]->(cls);
```

Step 2: Add Semantic Relationships

```
MATCH (m:Measurement), (p:Entity {id: "saref:Power"})
MERGE (m)-[:MEASURES_PROPERTY]->(p);
```

```
MATCH (w:WindTurbine), (e:Entity {id: "saref:Energy"})
```

```
MERGE (w)-[:PRODUCES]->(e);
```

```
MATCH (p:Entity {id: "saref:Power"}), (m:Measurement)
```

```
MERGE (p)-[:IS_MEASURED_BY]->(m);
```

```
MATCH (w:WindTurbine), (f:Entity {id: "saref:OnOffFunction"})
```

```
MERGE (w)-[:PERFORMS_FUNCTION]->(f);
```

Tips & Best Practices

- **Instance-class distinction:** Keep data instances separate from ontology concepts.
- **Avoid duplication:** Use MERGE instead of CREATE.
- **Validation:** Check your graph with simple queries:

```
MATCH (m:Measurement)-[:INSTANCE_OF]->(c)
```

```
RETURN m.id, c.id LIMIT 10;
```